

MEDICAL SCIENCES

NODULAR DESMOPLASTIC TRICHOBLASTOMA - CASE REPORT AND REVIEW OF DIAGNOSTIC CHALLENGES

Adrian Dragan

PhD.,

Braila County Emergency Hospital

“Dunarea de Jos” University, Galati – Romania

Dorina Stan

MD, PhD.,

Braila County Emergency Hospital

“Dunarea de Jos” University, Galati – Romania

D.F. Voicu

MD, PhD.,

Associated Profesor

“Dunarea de Jos” University, Galati – Romania

Abstract

Trichoblastoma is a benign follicular neoplasm, exhibiting differentiation toward primitive hair germ structures. Desmoplastic variants are rare and may closely resemble invasive cutaneous carcinomas both clinically and histologically.

The paper reports a nodular desmoplastic variant of trichoblastoma, arising on the scalp, in a 65-year-old woman. Four closely grouped nodules were initially present and completely excised. A fifth lesion developed at the same site 3.5 years later; no further recurrence occurred during another 5 years of follow-up. Histopathologic examination showed well-circumscribed dermal nodules, composed of cords and nests of basaloid cells, radiating from hyalinized stromal foci. Small foci of keratinization and mucinous change were observed. Deeper areas revealed spindle-shaped epithelial cells within a dense desmoplastic stroma, with focal infiltration of the epineurium and arrector pili muscle.

The nodular desmoplastic variant of trichoblastoma represents a rare benign follicular neoplasm, that can mimic morpheaform basal cell carcinoma and other desmoplastic adnexal tumors. Recognition of this entity is essential to prevent overtreatment.

Keywords: desmoplastic trichoblastoma, hair follicle neoplasm

Introduction

Trichoblastoma is a benign adnexal tumor, derived from primitive follicular germinative cells. Since its original description by Headington, several morphologic patterns have been identified, including nodular, retiform, and cribriform types. Desmoplastic trichoblastoma, though rare, is characterized by proliferation of basaloid cells within a dense, fibrotic stroma.

The histologic overlap between desmoplastic trichoblastoma and morpheaform basal cell carcinoma (BCC) poses a significant diagnostic challenge. Misinterpretation may lead to unnecessary extensive excision

or Mohs surgery. We report an unusual nodular desmoplastic variant of trichoblastoma, that further expands the histopathologic spectrum of this entity.

Case report

A 65-year-old woman presented with four firm, dome-shaped nodules on the parietal scalp. The lesions had slowly enlarged over several months but were asymptomatic (fig. 1). There was no personal or family history of skin cancer or adnexal tumors.

Fig. 1

Complete surgical excision was performed. Histopathology at that time confirmed a benign follicular tumor, consistent with trichoblastoma. After 3.5 years, a new lesion appeared at the previous surgical site and was excised. The patient has remained recurrence-free for another 5 years, since that procedure.

Microscopic examination revealed multiple well-circumscribed dermal nodules, separate from the overlying epidermis. The superficial portions contained compact hyalinized stromal nodules, from which cords

and nests of basaloid cells radiated outward, resembling follicular germ differentiation (fig. 2).

Focal keratinization and mucinous (mucoïd) change were noted within some epithelial islands. In deeper regions, the tumor cells acquired a spindle-shaped morphology and extended within a desmoplastic stroma. There was focal infiltration of the epineurium of small cutaneous nerves and involvement of arrector pili muscle fibers. No cytologic atypia, mitotic activity, or necrosis was presented.

Fig.2

All these findings supported a diagnosis of nodular desmoplastic trichoblastoma.

The immunohistochemical examination was not performed, although it would have been necessary, as a potential supportive evidence.

The differential diagnosis includes:

- Morpheaform Basal Cell Carcinoma - that shares stromal sclerosis, but shows nuclear atypia, mitotic activity, and peripheral palisading;

- Desmoplastic Trichoepithelioma - usually smaller, presents with central keratin cysts and lacks hyalinized stromal nodules;

- Desmoplastic Trichilemmoma - that is connected to the epidermis with clear cell change and trichilemmal differentiation.

Recognition of benign follicular architecture and absence of malignancy are critical for correct diagnosis.

Discussion

Desmoplastic trichoblastoma is an uncommon adnexal neoplasm, that can clinically and histologically simulate infiltrative carcinoma. The desmoplastic stroma and spindle cell morphology, in deeper sections, may give an impression of invasion. However, the lesion typically remains confined to the dermis, with well-defined margins and bland cytologic features.

Recurrence after complete excision is rare but may occur, as in this case. Long-term follow-up is recommended, though metastasis has never been reported.

Understanding the histopathologic spectrum of trichoblastoma is vital to avoid overdiagnosis and unnecessary aggressive management. Immunohistochemistry and clinicopathologic correlation further aid in accurate classification.

Conclusion

The nodular desmoplastic variant of trichoblastoma is a benign adnexal tumor, that may closely resemble invasive carcinomas, due to its desmoplastic stroma and spindle cell morphology. Awareness of this variant and its distinguishing features is crucial to prevent misdiagnosis and overtreatment. Our case adds to the limited literature describing this rare entity.

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